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ZARIA JOURNAL OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES IN EDUCATION PSYCHOSOCIAL FACTORS AND STUDENT ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN LAGOS STATE

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ABSTRACT

Academic performance has been a front-burner issue among stakeholders all over the world. This study, therefore, investigated the relationship between psychosocial factors and academic performance of secondary school students in District I Area of Lagos State. The study used three research questions and hypotheses. The research design used was the descriptive survey research design. The population of this study comprised all 4,726 public secondary school students in Education District I, Lagos State. The participants of the study comprised 368 participants who were selected using the multi-stage sampling technique. A self-constructed questionnaire titled Psychosocial Factors and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAFAPQ) was used to collect the data needed for the study, and the data collected from the participants were used to test the stated hypotheses using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics. The study found that there is a significant relationship between motivation, home environment, learning environment and students' academic performance in Education District I, Lagos State. The study therefore, recommended among other things that; the government should ensure that students are adequately motivated to make sure they are actively engage with the school programmes, the government should make school environment conducive and attractive to stimulate students' interest in school activities which will enhance students' academic performance, the government should make sure that adequate facilities are provided in the school system to stimulate students' interest in school programmes.

Keywords: Psychosocial Factors, Academic Performance, Teachers' motivation, Home environment, Learning environment.

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INTRODUCTION

Student academic performance is of great importance to stakeholders in education and forms a vital aspect of education. It refers to the knowledge students acquire, which is determined through grades in different subjects in a specific academic year or after a programme. Academic performance is of significant importance to stakeholders at all levels of education because it is a good indicator of the efficiency of institutions of learning, accurately evaluate students taking various subjects throughout a specific academic session, serves as a cautionary tale for the students to assess their performance level and make subsequent improvements, essential for obtaining good employment, building a successful career, and attaining a higher quality of life. Though it might appear to be a straightforward educational outcome, its impact on a nation is broad and far-reaching (Saumya et al., 2021). Academic performance has a great

influence on a student's self-esteem, social interaction, motivation, and perseverance in schools. Poor academic performance or high failure rates may result in unacceptable levels of attrition, reduced graduate throughput and increased cost of education. This also reduces admission opportunities for tertiary students seeking higher degrees. Academic performance, therefore, can be defined as student self-motivation, self-efficacy and the power to cope with the study environment to achieve excellence at secondary, college or university level.

According to Bakre and Alao (2023), educators and researchers have long been interested in identifying and understanding the variables that contribute to academic performance in schools. Researchers stated that these variables are internal and external to the school system, and they include demographic, environment, motivation, social interaction, socio-economic, family and school factors. The resultant argument

among researchers on the actual factors that influence students' academic performance necessitates this study to examine the relationship between psychosocial factors and student academic performance in secondary schools in Lagos State.

Psychosocial factor, as considered in this study according to Bakre and Alao (2023), refers to the psychological and social factors that may make or mar the study of a subject or course. Actually, motivation, learning environment, social interaction, home background and the interest of the student stand out as strong variables in explaining variation in the teaching and learning processes. Again, it could not be established that differences among school-related arrangements bear any direct, simple, universal relationship to teaching and learning, especially when some of the above-mentioned factors are held constant (Frayel, 2022). It is therefore expedient to investigate the roles of the psychosocial factors in predicting students' academic performance. Consequently, it should be noted that most students get a lot out of school. The highest variations in the teaching and learning observed around the basic levels may be attributed more to motivation, school learning environment, and social interaction than to school differences. Therefore, in order to promote effective teaching and learning, motivation, learning environment and home environment are pertinent factors that must be considered.

Motivation, as one of the psychosocial variables considered in this study, has become a major focus in education because of how much it can influence students' academic success. A student's level of motivation determines the level of students' engagement with school programmes and activities. Kunter et al. (2011), as cited in Nahid, Muzaffar & Abbas (2023), found that motivation helps to build classrooms that encourage active learning, participation, and critical thinking to influence the academic performance of students. Researchers (Nzabahimana & Opiyo, 2024; Oluoch & Gogo, 2022) found a positive correlation between motivation and students' academic performance.

In the same vein, the learning environment, as another variable considered in this study, encompasses the physical, psychological, and social conditions that influence how individuals learn. It's not just about the classroom; it includes all settings and factors that affect the learning process, both positively and negatively. A well-structured and resourceful learning environment has a strong influence on how well students perform academically. Key aspects such as the availability of physical resources, the overall classroom climate, and the nature of teacher-student interactions are essential. When these factors support learning, students are more likely to stay motivated, actively participate, and perform better in their studies. According to Akinyemi, Gbesoevi and Afolabi (2024), a well-equipped and supportive school environment significantly promotes effective teaching and learning, which in turn leads to improved academic performance. Conversely, when a school lacks essential learning resources and does not provide a conducive atmosphere, it hampers the ability of both teachers and students to perform at their best. Similarly, Jimoh (2025) emphasises that the learning environment is crucial in shaping students' academic outcomes, behaviour, and their reactions to various situations. It greatly influences how students interact and perform academically. Ikegbusi, Manafa and Iheanacho (2022) also attributed the poor teaching and learning in secondary schools to inadequate material and infrastructural resources, which are below expectations, with some schools having few classroom accommodations without windows, poor spacing and crowded seats, which significantly influence the academic performance of students.

On the issue of the home as a psychosocial factor, it is believed that management and control of the various indices at home can make or mar students' academic performance. Ikegbusi et al (2022) argued that a good home background and conducive environment tend to promote students' academic performance. Ajila and Olutola (2007) explained that the state of the home affects the individual since the parents are the first socialising agents in an individual's life. According to Ani and Osuji (2022), this is because the family background and concern of a

child affect their reaction to life situations and their level of performance. The home has a great influence on the students' psychological, emotional, social and economic state. However, one could deduce that the home is a recognised psychosocial factor having a lot of influence on students' academic performance. Researchers (Lueptow, 2015; Sui-Chu & Willms, 2016) found that there is a significant relationship between home environment and students' academic performance. However, Baumrind (2017) found that no significant relationship exists between home environment and students' academic performance. The disagreement among researchers necessitates a study of this nature to investigate the relationship between psychosocial factors and academic performance of secondary school students in Education District I Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, many students in secondary schools have been observed to exhibit low levels of motivation and commitment, which negatively impact their learning outcomes. In recent times, secondary education in Nigeria has faced increasing challenges in meeting the expected standards of quality teaching and learning. Factors such as inadequate school facilities, unmotivated students, unconducive home environments, and declining student interest have collectively hindered the effectiveness and productivity of the secondary school system. Also, it has indeed been observed today that there is persistent poor academic performance of students in both internal and external examinations. It appears that parents have lost confidence in the products of the public school system. The issue of academic performance is noticeable at every level of education in Nigeria and unless this trend is reversed, there will be poor quality output from the school system, wastage of resources, an increase in crime rate and drug addiction among youth, destruction of government properties, among others. This issue about the academic performance of students seems to be caused by certain psychosocial factors such as motivation, home environment and learning environment, which are the focus of this study. Therefore, there is a need for a study of this kind to investigate the influence of psychosocial factors on the academic

performance of secondary school students in Education District I, area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine the relationship between psychosocial factors and academic performance of secondary school students in Education District I, Lagos State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the relationship between motivation and students' academic performance
2. determine the relationship between learning environment and students' academic performance
3. investigate the relationship between home environment and students' academic performance

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

1. Is there any relationship between motivation and students' academic performance of secondary school students at Education District I, Lagos State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between the learning environment and students' academic performance in the study area?
3. What is the relationship between the home environment and students' academic performance?

Research Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between motivation and students' academic performance.

HO₂: Learning environment is not significantly related to students' academic performance.

HO₃: Home environment and students' academic performance are not significantly related.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive survey research design, and the population of the study was all the 4,726 Senior Secondary School 3 students in the Education District 1 Area of Lagos State, while the sample was 368 participants determined through the Taro Yemane formula for determining minimum sample size. The multi-stage sampling approach was used to select the participants of the study. The Education District was stratified into the existing zones (Agege,

Alimosho & Ifako-ijaye) after which the simple random sampling technique was used to select one zone (Agege) that participated in the study. The next stage involved the use of a proportionate sampling technique for the number of students who participated in each school. Thereafter, the simple random sampling technique was used to select the actual participants of the study. A self-designed instrument titled “Psychosocial Factors and Students’ Academic Performance Questionnaire” (PSFAPQ) was used for data collection.

The questionnaire was in two sections (A & B). Section A comprised structured items on psychosocial factors, while Section B was an English Language test that was used to measure students’ academic performance. The questionnaire was designed using the four-point Likert-type scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with a rating score of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively for positive items and otherwise for negative items. The research instrument was validated by experts in instrument construction while reliability was assured by administering the instrument on 30 participants who did not participate in the main study and data collected was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics and a reliability coefficient of .76 proved the instrument was reliable. The stated hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation statistics at .05 level of significance using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

The analysis of data collected is presented below.

Table 1: Motivation and Students’ Academic Performance

Variable	Mean	SD	N	Df	R	p	Decision
Motivation	8.32	3.14					Significant
Academic Performance	6.48	2.12	368	366	.81	.002	

Significant @ $p < .05$

Analysis in Table 1 shows that there is a strong, positive and significant relationship between motivation and academic performance in Education District I area of Lagos State ($r(368) = .81$; $df = 366$; $p < .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between motivation and

students’ academic performance, was rejected. This implies that motivation significantly relates to students’ academic performance in the Education District I area of Lagos State.

Table 2: Learning Environment and Students’ Academic Performance

Variable	Mean	SD	N	Df	R	P	Decision
Learning Environment	10.20	4.62					
Academic Performance	6.48	2.12	368	366	.58	.003	Significant

Significant @ $p < .05$

Results presented in Table 2 shows that there is a moderate, positive and significant relationship between home environment and students’ academic performance in Education District I area of Lagos State ($r(368) = .58$; $df = 366$; $p < .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between home environment and students’ academic performance was rejected. This implies that home environment significantly relate with students’ academic performance in Education District I area of Lagos State.

Table 3: Home Environment and Students’ Academic Performance

Variable	Mean	SD	N	Df	R	p	Decision
Home Environment	12.36	4.13					
Academic Performance	6.48	2.12	368	366	.71	.002	Significant

Significant @ $p < .05$

Findings in Table 3 shows that there is a strong, positive and significant relationship between home environment and students’ academic performance in Education District I area of Lagos State ($r(368) = .71$; $df = 366$; $p < .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between home environment and students’ academic performance was rejected. This implies that home environment significantly relates with students’ academic performance in the Education District I area of Lagos State.

DISCUSSION

Analysis in Table 1 shows that there is a strong, positive and significant relationship between motivation and academic performance in Education District I area of Lagos State ($r(368) = .81$; $df = 366$; $p < .05$). This implies that adequate motivation will enhance students’ academic performance in the school system. This

is in support of the findings by Harvey (2003), who confirmed that a significant relationship exists between motivation and academic performance. Similarly, it agrees with the findings of a study by French (2009) where it was found that a significant relationship exists between motivation and academic performance. This is also in support of the findings of a study by Kerlinger (2013) where it was established that a significant relationship exists between motivation and academic performance.

Results presented in Table 2 revealed that there is a moderate, positive and significant relationship between home environment and students' academic performance in Education District I area of Lagos State ($r(368)=.58$; $df=366$; $p<.05$) This implies that the quality of a students' environment in terms of parents' educational background, socio-economic status, occupation among others can have significant influence on students' academic performance in the school. The findings of this study agree with the research done by Lueptow (2015), where it was found that there is a significant relationship between home environment and students' academic performance. Similarly, it agrees with the findings of Sui-Chu and Willms (2016) which found that there is a significant relationship between home environment and students' academic performance. However, it contradicts the findings of Baumrind (2017) where it was found that no significant relationship exists between home environment and students' academic performance.

The result of the analysis of Hypothesis three ($r(368)=.71$; $df=366$; $p<.05$) showed that there is a significant relationship between learning environment and student academic performance. This implies that a favourable learning environment with the right type of facilities and equipment will motivate students to be highly committed to school programmes and activities, which in turn will lead to improved academic performance of students. This is in line with the findings of researchers (Crosnoe, 2004; Bali & Alvarez, 2004; Eamon, 2005) where it was found that a significant relationship exists between learning environment and student academic performance. Similarly, it agrees with the findings of a study by Yusuf (2004), who found

that a significant relationship exists between learning environment and student academic performance. It, however, contradicts the findings of a study by researchers (Glassman, 2004; Williams, 2008) where it was confirmed that no significant relationship exists between learning environment and student academic performance.

CONCLUSION

Psychosocial factors are critical to ensuring improved students' academic performance. Thus, if the school is to maintain a high level of students' academic performance, it must ensure that both teachers and students are placed within an accommodative educational framework, which entails a conducive environment for learning, implementation of policies that take into consideration the welfare of teachers, as well as collaboration of parents and teachers in the running of the school. Conclusively, students' academic performance can be improved if the necessary equipment and facilities are provided in schools because the adequacy of facilities will help make teaching and learning interesting for both students' and teachers. Similarly, the ability of parents to support students' learning at home will help strengthen students' competence with schoolwork. Therefore, all the variables considered in this study play a significant role in enhancing students' academic performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations are as follows:

1. The policymakers should design a policy that will ensure that students are adequately motivated in school to make sure they are actively engaged with school programmes and activities, which will help improve their academic performance.
2. The federal and state governments should make the school environment conducive and attractive to stimulate students' interest in school programmes and activities to improve students' academic performance.
3. The state government should make sure that adequate facilities are provided in the school system to stimulate students' interest in school programme and activities.
4. The state government and NGOs should provide training to parents in need of

supporting students at home to enhance their academic performance.

handbook of science education (pp. 1191–1239). Springer.

REFERENCES

- Ajao, A. (2011). Teachers' effectiveness in students' academic performance. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(2), 43-48.
- Akinyemi, I. A., Gbesoevi, E. S., & Afolabi, S. A. (2024). Exploring Classroom Environment as a Predominant Factor Affecting Students' Academic Performance in Lagos State Junior Secondary Schools, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Learning Research*, 1(2), 70–81.
<https://doi.org/10.62208/jelr.1.2.p.70-81>.
- Bakre, O. F. & Alao, O. S. (2023). Influence of mental health on senior secondary students' mathematics achievement in Educational District IV, Lagos State. *AKOKA Journal of Vocational Education*, 13(1), 147-154.
- Bali, V. A. & Alvarez. R. M. (2004). The race gap in student achievement scores: longitudinal evidence from a racially diverse school district. 2004. *Policy Studies Journal* 32(3), 393-416.
- Crosnoe, R. (2004). Social Capital and the Interplay of Families and Schools. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 66, 267-280.
- Crosnoe, R., Johnson, K. & Glen. H. E. (2004). School size and the interpersonal side of education: An examination of Race/Ethnicity and organizational context. *Social Science Quarterly*, 85(5), 1259-1274.
- Eamon, M. K. (2005). Social-demographic, school, neighborhood, and parenting influences on academic achievement of Latino young adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 34(2), 163-175.
- Frayel, R. (2022). Classroom learning environments: Retrospect, context, and prospect. In B. J. Fraser, K. G. Tobin, & C. J. McRobbie (Eds.), *Second international handbook of science education* (pp. 1191–1239). Springer.
- French, P. (2009). The Craft of Teaching: Learning, Assessment and Quality Assurance in Undergraduate Education Designing and Conducting Courses for Effective Learning in a Course–Credit Semester System. University of Ghana, Accessed from: <http://www.ug.edu.gh/aqau/sites/aqau/files/images/The%20Craft%20of%20Teaching.pdf>
- Glassman, N. S. (2004). Making better decisions about school problems: How administrators use evaluation to find solutions. California: Corwin Press.
- Harvey, S. (2003). Influence of teachers' motivation on students' performance in Certificate of Secondary Education in public secondary schools in Imenti South district Kenya, University of Nairobi.
- Ikegbusi, N. G., Manafa, F. U. & Iheanacho, R. C. (2022). Influence of school facilities on academic achievement of public secondary school students in Lagos State. *Journal of Educational Research & Development*, 5(2), 77-89.
- Jimoh, I. S. (2025). The impact of school environment and classroom management strategies on the behavior and academic outcomes of primary school pupils in Adavi Local Government, Kogi State, Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 10(6), 104-130.
- Kerlinger, F. N., & Howard, B. L. (2013). *Foundations of Behavioural Research* (4th ed., 890 p.). Wadsworth.
- Luetow, L. B. (2015). Parental status, influence and Achievement orientation of high school seniors. *Sociology of Education*, 48(1), 91-110.

- Nahid, S., Muzaffar, N. & Abbas, M. (2023). Impact of Teachers' Motivation on Students' Performance. *Global Educational Studies Review*, VIII(II), 444-453. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2023\(VIII-II\).40](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2023(VIII-II).40)
- Nzabahimana, M., & Opiyo, H. (2024). Effects of Teachers' Motivation on Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in Public Lower Day Secondary Schools in Rwanda: A Case of Kirehe District. *International Journal of Management and Development Studies*, 13(9), 97-116. <https://doi.org/10.53983/ijmds.v13n9.007>
- Oluoch, D. O., & Gogo, J. O. (2022). Relationship between intrinsic teacher motivation and teacher amotivation and student academic performance in public secondary schools in Gem Sub-County, Kenya. *African Educational Research Journal*, 134-142. <https://doi.org/10.30918/AERJ.102.22.020>
- Saumya, K., Agarwal, M. & Agarwal, N. (2021). Defining and Measuring Academic Performance of Hei Students: A Critical Review. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(6), 3091-3105.
- Williams, A. (2008). *Efficiency of education in ensuring sustainability of schools in developing countries*. *Journal of Quantitative Research*, 1(2), 102-114.
- Yusuf, S. (2004). Teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Measurement*, 1(3), 741-756.